

1 **Igf2 and an IGF2 family non-coding RNA are active in the stem cell to TE differentiation program.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of Igf2 as
9 a lineage commitment factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo. An IGF2 family non-coding
10 RNA was also a major target of modulation in the stem cell to TE differentiation program.

11 Citations

12 1. Sandovici, I., Georgopoulou, A., Pérez-García, V., Hufnagel, A., López-Tello, J., Lam, B.Y.,
13 Schiefer, S.N., Gaudreau, C., Santos, F., Hoelle, K. and Yeo, G.S., 2022. The imprinted Igf2-Igf2r axis is
14 critical for matching placental microvasculature expansion to fetal growth. *Developmental Cell*, 57(1),
15 pp.63-79.